

Greener vs Safer? A Systematic Literature Review on How Emissions and Safety shape Transport Research

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Abstract

This systematic literature review provides the first structured synthesis of current transport research that jointly studies emissions and road safety. Using the PRISMA protocol to analyze 86 journal and conference papers, we develop a rigorous and novel taxonomy based on eight methodological dimensions. The evidence is strongly skewed toward co-benefits: among studies reporting comparable changes in both emissions and conflict indicators, 47 reported reductions in both, and none reported increases in both. However, trade-offs remained evident: six studies found emissions reductions accompanied by increased conflicts, whereas two reported conflict reductions alongside higher emissions. Methodologically, the literature is dominated by microsimulation (with VISSIM and SUMO most common), with safety mainly assessed via post-run trajectory analytics especially surrogate safety measures (33 studies) and emissions reporting heavily centered on CO₂ (reported 54 times), most often quantified using HBEFA-based emission factors. Case-study evidence is concentrated to a large extent in China and the USA. Most experiments remain at junction/corridor-scale, with limited city-scale agent-based evaluation of behavioural mode-shift policies. Future work should therefore (i) develop large-scale, behaviourally validated models that treat emissions and safety as joint decision criteria in city-scale digital twins; (ii) expand monetized frameworks by incorporating external costs into agent decision-making, thereby enabling the evaluation of incentives and pricing policies; and (iii) improve mode-specific risk and severity representation, particularly for vulnerable road users, beyond exposure-based crash costing.

Keywords: Transport modelling, Agent-based modelling, Systematic literature review, Transport emissions, Road safety

1 Introduction

Transport emissions and road safety are two of the most pressing challenges confronting modern transport systems. Globally, the transport sector emitted 8.7 billion tons of greenhouse gases (expressed as CO₂-equivalent) in 2019, accounting for approximately 23% of all energy-related CO₂ emissions. Road vehicles were responsible for around 70% of these emissions [1]. In the UK, road transport alone contributes nearly 20% of total greenhouse gas emissions, and its CO₂ output has grown since the 1990s [2]. At the same time, road safety remains a critical challenge. More than 20,000 road fatalities were recorded across the EU in 2022 [3], with 1,633 occurring in the UK in 2023 [4]. These figures reflect the ongoing and intertwined policy challenges of reducing transport-related emissions while improving the safety of all road users.

Policies to cut transport emissions are often expected to make roads safer. One approach that demonstrates this dual benefit is increasing the penetration rate of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) while reducing the share of human-driven vehicles, which has been shown to improve both emissions and road safety [5]. Another approach is the use of advisory speed systems, which have proven effective in reducing both emissions and collision risk when compared to static limits [6]. Similarly, replacing conventional roundabouts with turbo roundabouts has been found to enhance both environmental and safety outcomes [7]. Figure 1 illustrates these examples of joint emissions and safety benefits.

Fig. 1 Examples of transport interventions that improve both emissions and safety

However, not all environmentally motivated measures guarantee safety gains. While roundabouts outperform signalized intersections in reducing emissions and conflicts for bicycles, conflict levels tend to increase with higher cycling volumes if infrastructure is not adapted accordingly [8]. A similar trade-off is observed in motorway lane restriction strategies for trucks, where limiting trucks to one or two lanes slightly reduces

emissions but increases safety risks compared to no restriction [9]. Crosswalk placement decisions show a similar tension: locating them near roundabout exits improves safety but increases emissions and delay, while midblock placement lowers emissions and delay but compromises safety [10]. These mutual interactions highlight the need for a unified framework capable of analyzing the dynamic relationship between emissions and safety outcomes. Figure 2 illustrates examples of these emissions–safety trade-offs.

Fig. 2 Examples of transport interventions involving emissions–safety trade-offs

Understanding the trade-offs between emissions and safety is essential before implementing transport policies in the real world, where changes to infrastructure, vehicle regulations, or operational strategies often involve not just significant financial costs, but also substantial time, coordination, and administrative effort. These decisions are rarely easy to reverse. In this context, transport simulation emerges as a powerful tool, offering a low-risk, flexible environment to test interventions, evaluate both environmental and safety outcomes, and uncover unintended consequences.

Despite these developments, there remains a limited body of research that rigorously studied the relationship between road safety and emissions. Only recently have studies begun to explore both dimensions together, a growing but still underdeveloped area of research. This review aims to address this gap by systematically examining transport studies that jointly assess emissions and safety, with particular attention to how they reveal synergies, tensions, and policy trade-offs.

In this paper, we delve into the nexus of vehicle emissions and road safety in transport research, aiming to characterize the state of the evidence, emerging methodological trends, and outstanding research gaps. Drawing on 86 journal and conference papers selected via a PRISMA-guided process, we synthesize how the literature evaluates

and interprets emissions–safety relationships and derive implications for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers by answering the following research questions:

Research Question 1: How do emissions and road safety interact in transport research, and which methodological and evaluation approaches distinguish these studies?

Research Question 2: What patterns of synergy and trade-off between emissions and road safety outcomes are observed in the literature, and what gaps remain for more integrated and policy-relevant evaluation?

Research Question 3: How does the emissions–safety evidence base vary across study contexts and intervention types? In particular, we explore:

(i) What themes, assessed measures, simulation tools, geographical contexts, and modelling scales dominate the literature?

(ii) What emission estimation methods, pollutant choices, safety assessment techniques (post-run vs in-simulation), and validation practices are most commonly used, and how do these choices vary across study themes?

To answer these research questions, this paper makes the following contributions:

1. A PRISMA-guided synthesis of 86 transport studies that evaluate both emissions and road safety, consolidating what has been studied.
2. A concept-driven taxonomy that classifies studies across key methodological dimensions, including simulation tools, assessed measures, case-study context, pollutant type, emission modelling approach, experiment scale, road safety approach, and validation approach.
3. A structured categorization of the reviewed corpus through two organizing lenses, study focus and road safety assessment approach, to enable consistent cross-study comparison.
4. A synthesis of reported synergies and trade-offs between emissions and safety outcomes, and of how studies evaluate and interpret the emissions–safety nexus.
5. A set of research and practice implications that highlight methodological gaps (e.g., validation, scalability, and coupling of emissions–safety mechanisms) and outline priorities for more integrated, policy-relevant evidence.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews related literature and explains how this study addresses the existing gap in the literature. Section 3 describes the PRISMA-based selection process and introduces the taxonomy and classification procedure used to systematically categorize the included studies. Section 4 reports the main findings and summarizes how studies assess the emissions–safety relationship. Section 5 reports additional descriptive results on simulation tools, modelling scale, geographical coverage, emission types and modelling methods, and validation practices. Section 6 concludes with key takeaways and directions for future research.

2 Related work

To identify the most relevant and recent literature reviews on transport and traffic simulation addressing the emissions–safety nexus, a structured search was conducted using the Scopus database. The focus was on review papers published between 2020 and 2025 in English-language journals. The following search query was applied to capture papers that combined transport simulation methods with review-oriented research:

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TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "transport simulation" OR "traffic simulation"  
OR "traffic simulator" OR "transport simulator" OR "agent-based  
model*" OR "agent-based simulation" OR "ABM" OR "MATSim" OR "SUMO"  
OR "SimMobility" OR "Aimsun" OR "VISSIM" OR "Anylogic" OR "NetLogo"  
OR "POLARIS" OR "TAPAS" OR "Repast" ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "literature  
review" OR "SLR" OR "systematic literature review" )
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As shown above, the search query does not explicitly include terms related to emissions or road safety. This decision was intentional, as including these terms within the Scopus title, abstract, and keyword fields resulted in just four review papers, none of which aligned with the objective of this study. Using this approach, the search returned 111 review papers. After excluding studies that did not address either the emissions or road safety dimension, a total of 21 papers were selected for review in this section. These comprise both narrative literature review and systematic literature review, as indicated in Table 1, below.

Table 1 Summary of Systematic Literature Reviews (SLR) and Literature Reviews (LR) in the last 5 years

Study	SLR or LR	Year	Range	Sample size	Area of Focus	Studied dimension (Emissions or Road safety)
[11]	LR	2022	2000 - 2019	not given	Connected and automated vehicles	Road safety
[12]	LR	2022	not given	not given	Spatiotemporal traffic prediction models	Road safety
[13]	LR	2022	2000 - 2022	61	Traffic signal optimization	Emissions
[14]	SLR	2025	2015 - 2024	not given	Connected and automated vehicles	Both
[15]	SLR	2023	2006 - 2022	309	ABM in Transport	Neither
[16]	LR	2020	not given	not given	ABM in Transport	Neither
[17]	SLR	2024	2013 - 2023	169	Connected and automated vehicles	Both
[18]	SLR	2025	2013 - 2022	154	ABM in Transport	Emissions
[19]	SLR	2025	not given	110	Activity based modelling in Transport	Neither
[20]	SLR	2025	2012 - 2024	26	Emission modelling	Emissions
[21]	SLR	2020	2013 - 2019	44	ABM and autonomous vehicles	Emissions
[22]	SLR	2021	2015 - 2020	80	ABM and autonomous vehicles	Emissions
[23]	LR	2023	1997 - 2023	not given	Emission modelling	Emissions
[24]	SLR	2025	2014 - 2024	14	Emission modelling	Emissions
[25]	LR	2022	2017 - 2022	not given	Travel behaviour and household location choices	Emissions
[26]	LR	2025	not given	not given	Activity based modelling in Transport	Neither
[27]	SLR	2022	1994 - 2020	160	Traffic signal optimization	Neither
[28]	LR	2023	not given	not given	Connected and automated vehicles	Road safety
[29]	SLR	2023	1996 - 2022	127	Human mobility and behaviour	Both
[30]	LR	2020	1992 - 2019	44	CA modelling for intersections	Both
[31]	SLR	2020	2005 - 2017	39	Health-related behaviour and outcomes	Both

Three of these studies have a primary road safety orientation. One study reviews spatiotemporal traffic-prediction techniques in general urban traffic systems, emphasizing their use for anticipating crash occurrence and severity rather than environmental outcomes [12]. Two further reviews focus on connected and autonomous vehicles and crash simulations, emphasizing how these technologies and detailed crash modelling can improve safety in heterogeneous traffic environments involving both human-driven vehicles as well as connected and autonomous vehicles, while mentioning emission effects only tangentially and without analyzing their interaction with safety outcomes [11, 28].

Another set of reviews focuses explicitly on emission modelling and simulators used to quantify vehicle emissions in urban networks [20, 23, 24]. These studies synthesize emission factor models and traffic–emission interfaces, propose frameworks for linking traffic conditions to emission estimation, and review how different microscopic and macroscopic simulators embed emission models. Their area of focus is consistently on emission modelling in general traffic and urban mobility systems, with safety outcomes absent from the scope of analysis. Emissions are treated as the sole performance dimension, and no attempt is made to relate environmental benefits to potential safety consequences or to articulate a safety–emissions trade-off.

A further set of reviews also takes emissions or environmental performance as a key concern, but within more specific substantive domains. One line of work centers on traffic signal optimization for sustainable transport, where signal control strategies at urban intersections are evaluated predominantly in terms of emission reductions and fuel savings rather than safety outcomes [13]. Other reviews examine accessibility, travel behaviour, and household location choices, or more broadly Agent-Based Models (ABMs) in urban transport, treating emissions and environmental sustainability as important evaluation criteria while still omitting explicit safety indicators [18, 25].

Related reviews on agent-based models and autonomous vehicles likewise discuss emissions and environmental impact in multiple sections, but do not incorporate road safety metrics or conflict measures in a systematic way [21, 22]. Taken together, these contributions embed emissions within richer behavioural and spatial analyses, yet still consider safety, if at all, only implicitly.

Several other reviews neither focus on emissions nor on road safety, but instead map broader methodological and modelling developments in transport. One such example is a review of reinforcement learning for urban network traffic control at signalized intersections focusing on control algorithms, and performance measures such as delay or throughput, without addressing emissions or safety explicitly [27]. Similarly, reviews of agent-based models and activity-based modelling synthesize frameworks and applications, including Mobility as a Service (MaaS), Demand Responsive Transport (DRT), and large-scale demand generation, prioritizing behavioural realism and model design over environmental or safety criteria [15, 16, 19, 26]. In these studies, the primary objective is to synthesize modelling elements, challenges, and application domains, environmental and safety outcomes lie outside the core scope and are not treated as evaluation criteria in their own right.

Only a small group of reviews engages with both emissions and safety within the same analytical frame [14, 17, 29–31]. Some of these consider connected and autonomous vehicles in rural areas or at roundabouts, discussing how such technologies may simultaneously reduce crash risk and promote sustainability through electric powertrains or smoother operations [14, 17]. Others adopt a multilevel perspective on human mobility and behaviour or review cellular automata models at signalized and unsignalized

intersections, where emissions (e.g. due to frequent acceleration–deceleration) and safety (e.g. conflict patterns, injury outcomes) are both reported [29, 30].

A further review synthesizes empirical and simulation evidence on health-related behaviours and outcomes, linking emission exposure and injury risk in transport systems [31]. However, even in these studies, emissions and safety are usually treated as separate outcomes examined within specific case studies or modelling tools, rather than as a broader trade-off that can be systematically compared across different modelling approaches and urban contexts. In contrast, this SLR aims to move beyond context-specific or tool-specific reviews by offering a broader synthesis of how various modelling approaches incorporate both emissions and road safety, and by placing the emissions–safety trade-off at the center of its analytical framework.

3 Methods

This section outlines the methodological approach used to conduct the literature review. Section 3.1 describes the selection criteria applied to identify relevant studies from the Scopus and Web of Science databases, following the PRISMA guideline to ensure transparency and rigor. The process of refining and excluding records is illustrated in detail to clarify how the final set of studies was determined. Section 3.2 presents a taxonomy developed to classify the selected studies according to their methodological characteristics. It comprises eight key dimensions: simulation tools, assessed measures, case-study context, pollutant type, emission modelling approach, number of simulated road users, road safety approach, and validation approach. Section 3.3 organizes these studies using two lenses (study focus and road safety assessment approach) providing a clear and consistent structure for presenting the evidence and setting up the results sections that follow.

3.1 Selection Criteria

Data for this literature review were collected from the Scopus and Web of Science indexed databases and subsequently refined according to the PRISMA guideline to eliminate irrelevant sources. Figure 3 provides a detailed overview of the search query and the study selection process conducted.

Initially, 737 records were identified in Scopus and 476 in Web of Science using the search query presented in Figure 3, making a total of 1,213 records. To enhance relevance, only journal and conference papers published in English were retained, resulting in 784 eligible records. No restrictions regarding publication year, subject area, or geographical location were imposed.

Subsequently, two exclusion rounds were conducted. In the first round, full-text screening eliminated an additional 507 records based on predetermined exclusion criteria: papers that did not specifically address transport modelling related to emissions or road safety. This included studies focused on medical research, air traffic management, platoon communication, nuclear energy systems, and maritime logistics, as well

as climate and environmental policy studies that did not examine transport-related emissions or safety, and land-based logistics research concerned with supply chains or freight operations rather than traffic-level emissions or safety outcomes. As a result, the total number of papers was reduced to 277.

In the second round, an in-depth full-text reading of these 277 papers led to the further exclusion of 191 papers. Ultimately, 86 journal and conference papers explicitly integrating transport modelling with both emissions and road safety were selected for the final analysis.

Fig. 3 Identification and selection process of studies for classification

3.2 Taxonomy

The taxonomy used in this review was developed following the iterative, concept-driven procedure proposed by Nickerson et al. [32]. In this method, a taxonomy is constructed by defining a meta-characteristic that determines the perspective and scope of the classification, and then iteratively identifying and refining dimensions and attributes so that objects of interest can be consistently classified.

The purpose of adopting this approach in this review is to provide a structured basis for classifying transport modelling studies that assess both emissions and road safety, thereby supporting systematic comparison of methodological and evaluation choices across the literature. This method was preferred because it offers a procedure with explicit design principles (meta-characteristic, iterative refinement, and ending conditions), which supports transparent, reproducible coding, an essential requirement for a systematic literature review.

In applying this procedure, the meta-characteristic was defined as the methodological and evaluation configuration of studies reporting both emissions and road safety outcomes. The dimensions and their attributes were then refined across successive iterations as additional papers were reviewed, until further screening no longer introduced new dimensions or required meaningful revisions to existing ones. The resulting taxonomy given in Table 2 comprises eight dimensions that characterize how each study is set up, modelled and evaluated.

Table 2 Taxonomy of methodological dimensions for the SLR

Dimension	Attributes
Simulation tools	VISSIM, SUMO, MATSim, Aimsun, PARAMICS, INTEGRATION, AnyLogic, ISR-TRAFSIM, EstiNet, DYNEMO, CARLA, AgentX, Custom-made Simulator
Assessed measures	Intersection control, Driving behaviour, Intersection designs, Post-event rerouting, Speed management, Corridor designs, Roundabout designs, Policy effect, Corridor control, Freeway lane change, Parking, Traffic lights, Dedicated lanes, Crosswalk placements, Hard shoulder, Bicycle safety, Route choice, Lane merging, Crosswalk designs, Pavement markings, Drop-off point designs, Ramp designs, Toll stations
Case-study context	Hypothetical network, Real-world network
Pollutant type	CO ₂ , CO, NO _x , HC, VOC, PM, SO ₂ , CH ₄ , GHG
Emission modelling approach	Instantaneous or micro-scale models, Factor-based or external tools and databases, Analytical or cost-based methods, formula-based methods
Simulated road users (count)	≤ 1,000, > 1,000 and < 100,000, ≥ 100,000
Road safety approach	Post-run analytics: SSM, Safety Proxy, MCDM, MSC Collision Avoidance Approaches: Centralized controller, Decentralized controller, Distributed controller.
Validation approach	No validation reported, Heuristic calibration, Statistical fitness metrics, Empirical comparison using non-standard or graphical criteria

The simulation tools dimension distinguishes between different microscopic and agent-based tools (e.g. VISSIM, MATSim, SUMO, Aimsun, other commercial or open-source simulators, and custom in-house models). Assessed measures captures the intervention or system features of each study, spanning 26 categories (e.g., control strategies, geometric and corridor designs, speed and lane management, etc), so studies can be compared based on what they evaluate rather than only on the outcomes they report.

Case-study context classifies whether studies use purely hypothetical networks, real-world networks in a single city/region/country, or multi-region/multi-country settings. Pollutant type records which emissions are explicitly modelled, differentiating among CO₂, CO, NO_x, HC, VOC, PM, and other pollutants (e.g. SO₂, CH₄). The Emission modelling approach groups methods into trajectory-based instantaneous models driven by second-by-second dynamics (e.g., VT-Micro; VSP), activity/factor-based approaches implemented via external databases or tools and simulator modules (e.g., HBEFA, MOVES), and higher-level analytical approaches, including formula-based estimates and life-cycle cost framework.

To characterize the size of each experiment, the simulated road users dimension classifies studies into three categories: small scale (fewer than 1,000 simulated users), medium to large scale (between 1,000 and 100,000), and very large scale (more than 100,000 simulated users). For safety, the road safety approach dimension distinguishes between studies that assess safety after the simulation has run and those that embed collision avoidance mechanisms within the simulation itself; the specific approaches are listed in Table 2 and described in Section 3.3.

The validation approach dimension distinguishes between no validation, heuristic calibration (trial-and-error parameter adjustment), validation based on statistical fitness metrics (e.g. GEH, MAPE, RMSE, NRMSE, R², RMSN), and direct empirical comparison using non-standard or graphical criteria (e.g. flow curves, fundamental diagrams, loop detector data).

3.3 Thematic classification and road safety assessment in the reviewed corpus

To present the findings of the reviewed studies the author considered two organizing lenses:

1. Thematic focus of the study
2. Road safety assessment approach

Together, these two lenses connect the objective of each study with the approach used to evaluate safety. Thematic categories cluster studies that address similar design or operational problems, while the safety assessment approach distinguishes whether

safety is treated as an outcome evaluated after the simulation run (post-run analytics) or as a constraint and control objective within the simulation (collision-avoidance logic). Together, they enable clearer cross-paper comparisons than purely technical grouping variables, which can vary without changing the underlying research question.

Furthermore, emissions were not used as a primary grouping criterion because many studies model more than one pollutant type. In contrast, each study typically adopts a single road safety assessment or collision-avoidance approach, with a small number of cases where this approach is used alongside MCDM frameworks.

Therefore, based on the intervention used and application context of each paper, the corpus was grouped into five study focus categories:

1. Geometric and physical design alternatives (23)
2. Driving behaviour, demand, and route choice impacts (7)
3. CV/AV/CAV market penetration effects on road junctions (16)
4. CV/AV/CAV communication impacts on traffic operations (21)
5. Traffic control, signal timing, and operational management strategies (19)

The number in parentheses indicates the number of studies in each study focus category. These thematic categories complement the methodological taxonomy dimensions (Table 2) by organizing the corpus into thematic intervention–context groupings, whereas the taxonomy dimensions systematically encode assessed measures alongside modelling and evaluation choices.

As mentioned before, road safety assessment methods fall into two broad families: post-run analytic approaches and collision-avoidance approaches implemented within the simulation. Post-run analytics quantify safety after the traffic simulation has completed, typically by processing simulated trajectories or traffic states, whereas collision-avoidance approaches modify behaviour during the simulation through controllers designed to prevent collisions. The distribution of these approaches across the reviewed corpus is summarized in Figure 4.

Fig. 4 Structure of the reviewed corpus by road safety assessment approach

Across the corpus, post-run analytics dominate. In particular, Surrogate Safety Measures (SSM) are the most common approach (33 studies), using indicators such as time-to-collision, post-encroachment time, deceleration profiles, and conflict counts derived from simulated trajectories [8, 33–35]. Safety proxy approaches appear in 11 studies and rely on traffic-level indicators (e.g., speed variance, hard braking, or lane-change frequency) as broader measures of driving volatility and risk [36–39]. Monetized Safety Cost (MSC), is used in seven studies, typically those oriented toward city-scale evaluation or longer-range policy analysis where safety is expressed in monetary terms [40–43].

Ten studies employ Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) frameworks e.g., Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) for weighting and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) for ranking to synthesize emissions and safety, and sometimes delay or cost, into composite scores to evaluate alternative designs and strategies [44–47]. As shown in Figure 4, MCDM therefore appears as a distinct evaluation pathway in the corpus, but in practice it often functions as an evaluation wrapper that incorporates another safety indicator (commonly SSM) rather than replacing the underlying safety measurement.

Collision-avoidance approaches focus on connected, automated, or cooperative systems (CV/AV/CAV and V2V/V2I settings). These approaches treat safety not as an outcome to be evaluated after the simulation, but as a constraint and control objective within the simulation itself, for example by dynamically adjusting vehicle speed, lane changing, or signal timing [48–51].

Within this family, centralized controllers are reported most frequently (14 studies),

followed by decentralized controllers (8 studies) and distributed controllers (3 studies), as summarized in Figure 4. The distinction between these controller types lies in how decision-making authority is structured. In centralized control, a single control unit determines vehicle or signal behaviour for the system as a whole, for example, an intersection management system that coordinates vehicle movements or optimizes signal phases from one authority [50].

In decentralized control, each vehicle makes its own decisions locally without a central coordinator, such as in post-event rerouting where individual vehicles independently select alternative routes after detecting congestion or an incident [52]. In distributed control, multiple controllers operate across the network and coordinate with one another using V2V/V2I communication, sharing decision-making responsibility without relying on a single point of control. Examples include eco-driving schemes in which vehicles coordinate speed and acceleration patterns by coordinating with other vehicles and infrastructure to enhance both safety and environmental performance [53].

Overall, while all reviewed studies report both emissions and at least one road safety indicator or collision avoidance approach, they differ in whether safety is primarily assessed after the simulation run using analytic measures and proxies, or embedded during simulation via collision-avoidance control logic. This distinction is central for interpreting the taxonomy, because it shapes how tightly safety is coupled to simulated traffic dynamics and to the operational or design strategies being evaluated.

4 Results

To present the findings from the reviewed studies, this section is organized into the following subsections: Section 4.1 summarizes what was assessed in the studies, grouping the wide range of transport interventions and system features into consistent study focus categories. Section 4.2 then examines how these interventions jointly affect emissions and conflict-based safety indicators, highlighting where results fall into Win–Win outcomes versus explicit trade-offs. Section 4.3 synthesizes post-run analytic studies that use safety and emission indicators, distinguishing between surrogate safety measures, safety proxies, multi-criteria approaches, and monetized external costs, with Section 4.3.1 focusing specifically on the subset that reports monetized safety costs. Finally, Section 4.4 reviews collision-avoidance control studies with connected vehicles, comparing different controller types and penetration scenarios in terms of their implications for emissions and safety.

4.1 What was assessed in the studies?

Across the reviewed literature, we examined a wide range of transport related features and interventions, spanning infrastructure layout, traffic management and control, behavioural responses, and connected-vehicle capabilities. These assessed aspects were consolidated into 26 assessed measures and mapped onto the five study focus categories defined earlier. Figure 5 illustrates this mapping, showing how each assessed theme

connects to one or multiple study focus, and where the strongest concentrations of attention lie.

Fig. 5 Links between assessed measures and study focus in the reviewed studies

Geometric / Physical Design Alternatives: A substantial strand of work evaluated changes to the physical form of the traffic network by comparing alternative layouts and design options. This included corridor-level redesigns, including Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) corridor scenarios and other corridor layout alternatives, as well as intersection-level redesigns that tested different junction configurations under comparable conditions [33, 41, 44–47, 54, 55].

Roundabouts were treated both as their own design family and as comparators to

other junction forms, including evaluations of conventional versus modified/turbo-style concepts [7, 35]. Pedestrian-focused physical interventions were also examined via crosswalk placement and crosswalk design variations, complemented by smaller-scale elements such as pavement markings [10, 56, 57]. Several studies also assessed access and transfer geometries such as drop-off point designs and ramp designs as part of broader layout optimization [58, 59].

Traffic Control, Signal Timing, and Operational Management Strategies: Studies in this focus assessed operational measures applied to existing networks, including how speed, lane use, and control settings are managed to improve performance. A large share examined speed management, such as variable speed limits, speed advisory approaches, and work zone/area wide speed control, typically comparing alternative strategies under different traffic conditions [6, 60–62]. Hard shoulder operations were also evaluated through different opening/closing strategies as demand changes, treating shoulder use as a dynamic congestion management tool [63, 64].

Several studies focused on signal related operations, including comparisons of intersection control strategies and signal timing plans, alongside in-vehicle support at signals to reduce inefficient stopping [65–67]. Additional operational topics included parking/access management and toll station operations, as well as manoeuvre-critical conditions such as lane merging and operational lane-use restrictions [39, 68–70].

Driving Behaviour, Demand, and Route choice impacts: In this study focus, assessments centred on how traveller behaviour and demand patterns shape outcomes, rather than changes to infrastructure or connectivity. Some studies tested route choice by comparing multiple alternative routes for different modes (e.g., bike and car) to observe how routing decisions shift performance [34]. Others examined bicycle safety through scenario testing that increased bicycle demand in steps and evaluated how changing cycling volumes affected safety-related outcomes under fixed network conditions [8].

Demand sensitivity was also assessed via time-of-day demand scenarios (e.g., contrasting peak and off-peak demand conditions) to understand how system outcomes change when travel demand redistributes across the day [37]. Finally, several studies evaluated policy and demand-future effects by comparing alternative policy packages or AV-demand/fleet transition scenarios to quantify how different behavioural and demand futures translate into system-level impacts [40, 42, 43].

CV/AV/CAV Communication impact on Traffic Operations: Communication-focused studies examined how connectivity and coordination mechanisms influence operational performance. A dominant theme was intersection control, where studies evaluated cooperative or connected control approaches under varying traffic conditions, often benchmarking against conventional signal control [49–51, 71].

Beyond intersections, studies examined V2V/V2I-enabled coordination for corridor

control, freeway lane-changing, and post-event rerouting, showing how information exchange can improve both routine operations and disruption management [53, 72–74]. Others used connected information to shape behaviour via eco-driving support (e.g., speed guidance to smooth trajectories and avoid unnecessary stops) or learning-based driving (data-driven control that adapts decisions over time), with a smaller subset extending these approaches to bicycle safety in connected-vehicle environments [75–77].

CV/AV/CAV Market Penetration Rate effect on Road Junction: Market-penetration studies examined how network and junction performance changes as the share of autonomous and connected and autonomous vehicles increases, typically by testing multiple penetration levels under otherwise comparable conditions. A strong emphasis was placed on junction operation and control, assessing how intersection performance and the effectiveness of control strategies shift as adoption rises [38, 78–80].

Penetration effects were also tested for freeway lane-changing and lane merging, since these manoeuvres depend heavily on how automated and human-driven vehicles respond to one another, which can change congestion, delay, and throughput [81, 82]. Other studies evaluated whether dedicated lanes become more beneficial as adoption increases [83]. In addition, some varied the driving assumptions used in the simulation (such as following distance and gap acceptance) across adoption levels, showing that these behavioural settings can materially change the results as the vehicle mix shifts [5, 48, 84, 85].

Overall, Figure 5 shows that certain assessed themes, most notably intersection control, driving behaviour, and post-event rerouting appear across multiple study focus, indicating that they are repeatedly used as cross-cutting features to link design, operations, behavioural change, and connected and autonomous vehicle related effects within the reviewed evidence base.

4.2 Trade-off in Emissions and Conflicts

To understand whether interventions deliver co-benefits or trade-offs, we compare studies that quantify changes in both emissions and conflicts. Because emissions and safety outcomes were reported using different indicators and units across the reviewed studies, the percentage change in emissions ($\Delta E\%$) and percentage change in conflicts ($\Delta C\%$) was used to normalize results and enable consistent comparison. Figure 6 illustrates the quadrant map, focusing on the subset of studies reporting both $\Delta E\%$ and $\Delta C\%$, allowing each intervention to be interpreted as a Win–Win (both decrease) or a trade-off (one improves while the other worsens).

In total, 57 studies report both metrics and are plotted in Figure 6. Four geometric design applications assess safety qualitatively within a multi-criteria framework, so no percentage change in conflicts is available for these studies. Additional collision-avoidance studies incorporate safety controllers but do not report post-simulation

changes in conflicts, meaning they also cannot be included here. Across the plotted evidence, results are strongly concentrated in the Win–Win quadrant, and no study falls within the Lose–Lose quadrant.

Fig. 6 Trade-offs between emissions and conflict-based safety outcomes

The reported evidence places intersection designs primarily in the Win–Win region. The category-specific kernel density estimate (KDE) shown in Figure 6 concentrates its highest density around moderate co-benefits (roughly $\Delta E\% \approx -20\%$ to -40% and $\Delta C\% \approx -20\%$ to -40%). Within this spread, a study on U-turn intersection layouts delivers the largest emissions reductions with the design where left-turning vehicles are redirected to median U-turns, and the required crossovers are controlled by traffic signals to manage merging and crossing movements [33]. Another study on intersection redesigns yields the strongest conflict reductions where a roundabout was converted to a pinavia [86].

Driving behaviour interventions likewise cluster in the Win–Win space, where the KDE forms a pronounced diagonal ridge in Figure 6, with peak density around moderate co-benefits (approximately $\Delta E\% \approx -20\%$ to -35% and $\Delta C\% \approx -50\%$ to -85%), indicating that larger emissions improvements tend to coincide with larger conflict reductions in this subset. The upper-end co-benefit (up to $\sim -55\%$

emissions and $\sim -100\%$ conflicts) is reported in the study examining connected and autonomous vehicles on a grid urban network under different driving behaviours, where shifting from 100% human-driven vehicles to 100% connected and autonomous vehicles (under normal driving behaviour at 3000 vph) yields the largest simultaneous reduction in both emissions and conflicts [84].

Speed management interventions are also predominantly favourable, with most density located in the Win–Win region, but with a broader spread than intersection control and driving behaviour, with peak density around modest emissions reductions paired with moderate conflict reductions (roughly $\Delta E\% \approx -5\%$ to -15% and $\Delta C\% \approx -10\%$ to -40%), and a secondary lobe extending toward very large safety gains (around $\Delta C\% \approx -90\%$ to -100%) at similarly modest emissions improvements. Within this spread, the largest emissions reduction is reported in a study that used a smart speed-control system to smooth traffic and prevent stop-and-go driving (about $\Delta E\% \approx -26\%$, alongside $\Delta C\% \approx -31\%$) [62]. The strongest conflict reduction is observed in the study about variable speed limit control strategy for freeway work zones using a discrete-time sliding mode controller (about $\Delta C\% \approx -97\%$) with a smaller emissions benefit ($\Delta E\% \approx -7\%$) [87].

Intersection control interventions are similarly concentrated in the Win–Win space, where the KDE in Figure 6 forms a clear diagonal ridge, with peak density centered on moderate co-benefits (approximately $\Delta E\% \approx -10\%$ to -15% and $\Delta C\% \approx -30\%$ to -45%), indicating that stronger emissions reductions tend to align with stronger conflict reductions within this subset. While KDE smoothing extends slightly across the zero axes, the underlying study points remain in the lower-left quadrant, spanning from near-neutral changes (about $\sim -3\%$ emissions and $\sim -1\%$ conflicts) to substantial co-benefits. The upper-end co-benefit is reported in a study in which an advanced intersection control strategy using multi-agent reinforcement learning to create smarter traffic lights yields the largest reduction in both emissions ($\Delta E\% \approx -32\%$) and conflicts ($\Delta C\% \approx -55\%$) [65].

Beyond these dominant clusters, post-event rerouting sits mainly in the Win–Win space, where disruption-aware rerouting dampens secondary interactions while also delivering modest emissions benefits [88, 89]. Corridor and roundabout design interventions are likewise mostly Win–Win, indicating that network and junction reconfiguration can simultaneously reduce conflict exposure and improve operational efficiency [7, 35, 54]. For broader system interventions, policy effect measures that drive the network-wide mode shifts show co-benefits in the plotted set, though magnitudes are typically lower than geometry/control interventions [40, 43].

Parking interventions also land in the Win–Win quadrant in the available evidence, consistent with the idea that reducing parking-related circulation and friction can lower both conflict exposure and emissions [68, 69]. Finally, the “Other” category captures the remaining assessed measures shown in Figure 5. Many of these measures are represented by only one or two studies, so plotting each separately would add

clutter without adding interpretive value. They are therefore grouped for readability, while still contributing to the overall pattern. Most points remain in the Win–Win space, with a smaller subset in the trade-off quadrants.

Despite the dominance of Win–Win findings, a smaller subset of studies reveals clear trade-offs, and these are important because they show where “emission” and “safety” do not automatically align. One recurring pattern is emissions reductions accompanied by increased conflicts. For corridor-oriented interventions, one study comparing multiple corridor alternatives shows that the configuration delivering the lower emissions can still be associated with degraded safety outcomes. In this case, the highest-ranked alternative (Alternative 5), which combined VISSIM-optimized signal control at one intersection with an at-grade channelized redesign at another while retaining existing layouts elsewhere, achieved notable efficiency and emission reductions but exhibited higher conflict-related safety values. This finding suggests that operational efficiency gains (e.g., higher throughput or different traffic flow patterns) may intensify interaction density or complexity in ways that elevate conflict rates [44].

A similar trade-off appears in crosswalk placement changes: locating them near roundabout exits improves safety but increases emissions and delay, while midblock placement lowers emissions and delay but compromises safety, suggesting that reorganizing pedestrian–vehicle encounter geometry can inadvertently raise interaction risk even when it reduces delay and idling [10, 90]. Trade-offs of the same type also emerge in operational control contexts such as traffic lights optimization and dedicated lanes (truck restriction strategies), where emissions improvements are achieved but conflicts rise slightly. This suggests that performance-driven control and capacity allocation can redistribute interaction hotspots [9, 66].

Similarly, a trade-off is observed for policy effect, where a fleet transition from conventional cars to electric cars delivers a substantial emissions decrease while conflicts increase, highlighting that cleaner-vehicle transitions do not automatically translate into improved interaction safety unless complemented by measures that also address behaviour and operational conflict mechanisms [42].

The opposite trade-off, where conflicts decreasing while emissions increase, is also observed, reinforcing that “safer” does not always mean “greener”. For pavement marking design alternatives, the configuration associated with fewer conflicts is paired with higher emissions, consistent with scenarios where added caution, lower speeds, or more constrained manoeuvring reduces interaction severity but increases travel time or inefficiency [56]. Likewise, a speed management study of traffic-calming measures (notably a 30km/h zone) in a residential area reports fewer conflicts but a slight increase in emissions, suggesting that while the intervention reduces risky interactions, it can also prolong travel time or keep vehicles operating less efficiently from an emissions perspective [91].

In addition to these opposing-direction trade-offs, two studies report safety gains

without measurable emissions change. In a connected environment, one study reduces conflicts by prioritizing cyclists at intersections over vehicles, while emissions remain stable due to minimal changes in speed and acceleration [77]. Another separates traffic streams using dedicated lanes, lowering conflicts but without system-wide smoothing, so emissions stay largely unchanged [83].

Overall, the joint-evaluation evidence indicates that most interventions deliver co-benefits, with the quadrant map heavily concentrated in the Win–Win space and only a small number of studies exhibiting trade-offs. This pattern is summarized in Table 3: forty seven studies report simultaneous reductions in emissions and conflicts, while trade-offs are comparatively rare (e.g., six cases with lower emissions but higher conflicts, and two with higher emissions but lower conflicts). In addition, two studies achieve safety gains without measurable change in emissions, and no studies fall into the Lose–Lose category.

Table 3 Cross-tabulation of emissions and conflicts outcomes

		Conflicts		
		Lower	Unchanged	Higher
Emissions	Lower	47	0	6
	Unchanged	2	0	0
	Higher	2	0	0

4.3 Post-run analytic studies using safety and emission indicators

Figure 7 maps the 61 post-run analytic studies with road safety approaches, emissions, and the overall study focus. Geometric or physical design alternatives form the largest cluster (23 studies), followed by traffic control, signal timing, and operational management strategies (19 studies). Smaller groups address CV/AV/CAV market penetration rate effects at road junctions (8 studies), driving behaviour, demand, and route choice impacts (7 studies), and CV/AV/CAV communication impacts on traffic operations (4 studies).

Fig. 7 Links between safety methods, emission types, and study focus

Across these 61 studies, SSM are the dominant analytic approach, but the balance shifts by study focus. In geometric or physical design applications, SSM is applied in 10 studies and MCDM in 9, reflecting their widespread adoption in evaluating alternative design options [33, 35, 46, 92]. In two of these cases, MCDM is explicitly applied alongside SSM within the same evaluation framework [93, 94]. MSC also features in four design studies, reflecting a smaller but consistent strand where safety outcomes are expressed as monetized impacts to support direct comparison alongside emissions [41, 86, 95, 96].

Safety proxy indicators are less common in this group (5 studies). Among these, two studies rely solely on safety proxies without additional multi-criteria tools [55, 57]. In contrast, three studies integrate safety proxy indicators with MCDM, highlighting efforts to support trade-off evaluations even where detailed conflict modelling is absent [44, 56, 59].

A similar pattern emerges in traffic control, signal timing, and operational management studies. Out of 19 such applications, 12 rely on SSM to compare alternative control and operational strategies [60, 61, 63, 68]. Six further studies use safety proxies, typically combining measures such as speed variability, queue dynamics, or critical

decelerations to reflect crash risk in operational decision contexts [36, 39, 66, 67]. MCDM is used alongside safety proxy indicators in only one study, to evaluate three alternative truck lane restriction strategies on motorway [9]. MSC does not appear in this strand, suggesting that operational studies more often retain surrogate indicators rather than translating safety outcomes into monetized terms.

In contrast, connected vehicles focused work draws almost exclusively on SSM. All four communication-focused studies use SSM-based safety indicators [71, 75, 77, 88]. In the market penetration strand, six of the eight studies adopt SSM, while two use safety proxies [5, 38, 78, 82]. Driving behaviour, demand, and route choice impacts are the main exception: three studies use SSM and three use MSC, with one further safety-proxy application [34, 37, 40, 42].

On the emissions side, pollutant coverage also varies by study focus rather than simply mirroring overall frequency. In geometric or physical design alternatives, CO is most common (15 of 23 studies), followed by NO_x (10) and CO₂ (9), with VOC appearing in a smaller subset and only isolated inclusion of HC and PM [10, 33, 35, 44]. Traffic control and operational management studies broaden the pollutant set and emphasize NO_x (15 of 19), alongside substantial reporting of CO₂ (12) and CO (11), consistent with interventions that act directly on stop-start dynamics and speed variability [36, 60, 63, 67].

In connected vehicle market penetration studies, CO₂ remains the most prevalent (6 of 8), but NO_x, CO, and HC each appear in three studies, with occasional inclusion of CH₄, SO₂, and PM [5, 38, 78, 83]. Communication-focused CAV studies report CO₂ as the sole pollutant in this study focus [71, 75, 77, 88]. Finally, in driving behaviour, demand, and route choice impacts, CO₂ dominates (6 of 7), while NO_x is less frequent (4 of 7) and other pollutants appear only sporadically [8, 34, 40, 97]. Overall, Figure 7 highlights that post-run analytic studies are characterized by SSM-led safety evaluation combined with CO₂-centered emission metrics, with the broadest pollutant coverage concentrated in traffic control and operational management applications [36, 60, 63, 67].

Figure 8 shows the percentage change in emissions ($\Delta E\%$, horizontal axis) against the percentage change in conflicts ($\Delta C\%$, vertical axis) for the 57 post-run analytic studies. In contrast to Figure 6, the studies are grouped here by road safety method rather than by the assessed intervention.

Fig. 8 Percentage changes in emissions and conflicts for post-run analytic studies.

SSM accounts for the majority of plotted studies and largely generates the main KDE peak. The SSM points are most tightly concentrated around modest emissions reductions paired with comparatively larger conflict reductions, with only a small number of outliers away from the dominant cluster. This reinforces that, in the post-run analytic literature, SSM-led evaluation is most commonly associated with dual-benefit outcomes rather than systematic safety-emission trade-offs [33, 60, 71, 89].

Safety proxy studies form a smaller cluster that overlaps the same high-density area. In other words, proxy-based studies show the same overall pattern as the full set of

results, emissions and conflicts usually improve together, but the changes are typically more moderate, with fewer extreme values in either direction [36, 39, 57, 67].

Multi-criteria approaches show a clearer separation in Figure 8. MCDM using SSM aligns with the main KDE mass, whereas MCDM using safety proxies is more scattered and is more represented among the trade-off points, suggesting that proxy-based formulations are more likely to expose explicit trade-off between emissions and conflict outcomes in the evaluated option sets [9, 56, 93, 94].

MSC studies also sit mainly within the joint-improvement region, but are visibly more dispersed than safety proxies. A consistent interpretation is that, in MSC studies, similar emissions reductions can be accompanied by quite different magnitudes of conflict reduction, so safety shifts are more variable even when emissions changes are comparable [40, 43, 95, 96].

4.3.1 Post-run analytic studies using monetized safety cost

A subset of post-run analytic studies adopts the MSC approach, reporting both emissions and safety outcomes as percentage changes in external costs. There are seven such studies, covering intersection design (4 studies) and policy effect (3 studies). In the intersection design strand, studies that uses MSC fall in the Win–Win quadrant in Figure 6, indicating simultaneous reductions in both emissions and crash related costs [41, 86, 95, 96]. The policy effect strand, in contrast, uses MSC to examine how behavioural change and fleet transition interventions (including electrification of on-demand services) alter the external costs associated with emissions and crashes.

In a Berlin-based case study that uses MATSim, an agent-based simulation tool, researchers evaluated how introducing stop-based autonomous electric shuttles, combined with a complete ban on private cars, would reshape environmental and safety outcomes in a dense urban setting. Under this scenario, the model revealed significant improvements in key externalities: road safety externality costs fell from €1,139 million to €909.5 million, a reduction of around 20%, largely due to the elimination of private-car crashes and the built-in safety advantages of automated shuttle operations. Emissions-related externality costs also declined, dropping from €123,250 million to €117,300 million, a decrease of about 4.8%, driven by the sharp reduction in private car travel and a corresponding shift toward shared electric shuttles, walking, and cycling [40].

The Chicago-based ridesourcing electrification study uses AgentX, another agent-based modelling tool, to compare Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) and Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV) operations, highlighting a clear environmental improvement alongside a modest trade-off in road-related impacts. When the fleet transitions from ICE to BEV operation, Green House Gas (GHG) external costs per trip fall from 0.22¢ to 0.13¢, representing a 40.9% reduction, consistent with the broader model

findings that electrification substantially lowers lifecycle greenhouse gas emissions. At the same time, additional travel required for BEVs to reach charging infrastructure increases vehicle miles traveled, raising traffic externalities, including congestion, crashes, and noise from \$1.30 to \$1.40 per trip, a 7.69% increase. This scenario therefore illustrates how electrification meaningfully decreases climate-related damages while slightly elevating traffic-related societal costs [42].

In the third policy effect study, researchers used MATSim to evaluate how alternative future mobility strategies could reshape travel behaviour in Hamburg. The Base2019 scenario represents the 2019 transport system (pre-COVID) and provides the benchmark for comparison. ProClimate2030 introduces strong “push” measures, such as increased parking pressure, widespread 30 km/h speed limits, and lane reductions, to reduce the attractiveness of private vehicles. Among the explored futures, ProClimate2030 produced the strongest combined benefits, achieving a 6.10% reduction in emissions and a 10.10% reduction in accident costs relative to Base2019. In contrast, the RealLab2030 scenario, which relies mainly on “pull” measures such as shared mobility services, improved cycling infrastructure, and a €2.50 daily incentive for individuals who avoid car use entirely, produced only marginal reductions. The study attributes this to limited system-wide mode shift, indicating that incentive-based approaches alone were insufficient to generate substantial emissions or safety-cost improvements [43].

Across these policy effect studies, a notable limitation is that external costs are treated as static and are calculated post-simulation, meaning they do not influence agent decision-making during the simulation itself. The Hamburg study includes a financial incentive in one scenario, but the limited change in modal share suggests that the incentive implemented as part of the scenario design rather than as an endogenous behavioural mechanism had minimal effect on reducing emissions and accident costs. This points to a clear research gap: closer integration of behavioural dynamics and mode-specific safety modelling is needed so that monetized incentives and external costs can directly shape agent choices during simulation, providing a more robust basis for evaluating urban transport policies.

Another limitation is that the crash-cost calculation adopted across these studies is highly simplified, and is commonly estimated by multiplying Vehicle Kilometres Travelled (VKT) by Germany’s fatality rates, or per-kilometre crash-cost factors from the literature, or values taken from German transport appraisal handbooks [40, 42, 43]. While this exposure based method offers a straightforward estimate of risk by considering distance travelled, it does not capture several critical contextual dimensions, such as, accident severity (e.g., fatal, serious, slight), time and location of occurrence, and the types of road users involved (e.g., pedestrians and cyclists).

4.4 Collision-avoidance control with connected vehicles

Within the collision-avoidance approach, Figure 9 links 25 studies across four elements: studies, controller type, emissions, and overall study focus. Since all the studies

fall into two focus areas, the sample is split between applications that use CV/AV/-CAV communication to influence traffic operations at signals and along corridors, and those that examine how increasing CV/AV/CAV market penetration affects safety and emissions at junctions and corridors. Across these 25 studies, centralized controller is the most dominated approach used in 14 studies, with decentralized in 8 and fully distributed controllers in 3.

Fig. 9 Links between controller types, emission types, and study focus

In studies focused on CAV communication and traffic operations, most interventions are tested against standard current practice. For intersection control, centralized approaches typically coordinate vehicle movements to reduce stopping and harsh acceleration, and they are compared with base cases such as fixed-time or actuated traffic lights or standard (non-cooperative) intersection control, across these studies, the coordinated CAV strategies generally reduced emissions versus the traffic-light / conventional baselines [49–51, 98].

For post-event rerouting (e.g., after an incident) studies commonly compare “no communication / no Road Side Unit (RSU)” scenarios with cases where vehicles receive

warnings, guidance, or rerouting via V2V/V2I. These communication-enabled interventions also lower emissions relative to the no-communication base cases [52, 53, 99]. Decentralized (vehicle-by-vehicle) methods are usually assessed as driving assistance compared with no-assistance or simpler rule-based driving, and they tend to deliver smaller but still positive emission reductions [74, 76].

In the CAV market penetration studies, the key assessment is how emissions change as the share of connected/automated vehicles increases, usually by comparing a low/zero-penetration baseline (often 0%) with higher penetration scenarios. Centralized strategies are assessed using different intersection “right-of-way” or coordination rules, compared to base cases such as conventional control (e.g., four-way stop or standard intersection operation without coordination). These studies generally find that centralized coordination reduces emissions compared with the conventional baseline, especially when vehicle passing order and timing are designed to avoid stop-and-go traffic [80, 81, 100].

Decentralized strategies are assessed as vehicle level eco-driving or manoeuvre decision-making across a range of operating conditions (e.g., dry, wet, or snowy roads, varying congestion levels, and blocked-lane incidents). They are typically evaluated against base cases with no eco-driving support/no assistance or lower CAV penetration. Overall, decentralized approaches reduce emissions relative to the corresponding baselines, although the magnitude of the benefit varies with both traffic conditions and the penetration rate [48, 79, 101, 102].

Only one study adopts a distributed approach, comparing three scenarios: human-driven vehicles; connected vehicles receiving eco-approach advice (i.e., speed guidance when approaching a junction so the vehicle arrives during a green phase or at an allocated time slot, thereby reducing stopping); and fully cooperative CAVs. The baseline scenario consists of all conventional vehicles. The cooperative case reduced emissions relative to this baseline [103].

Figure 10 illustrates how emission reductions vary by controller type in these studies. Centralized controllers cut emissions the most, on average about 30%, with most results falling between roughly 15% and 49%. Decentralized controllers deliver smaller, steadier gains about 7% on average, with most results between roughly 6% and 17% reductions. Distributed controllers sit in the middle, with typical cuts around 19%, in this small sample, results lie between roughly 13% and 22%. In short, across the 25 studies analyzed here, centralized controllers achieve the largest but most variable reductions, while decentralized and distributed controllers provide steadier mid-range improvements.

Fig. 10 Emission reductions by controller type in collision-avoidance studies

5 Review of methodological approaches

To extend the findings from the previous section, this section is organized into the following subsections: Section 5.1 maps the reviewed studies by simulation tools and study focus categories, with VISSIM and SUMO emerging as the most frequently used. Section 5.2 then profiles study scale, with simulated road users ranging from 34 to 750,000 across the literature. Section 5.3 synthesizes the geographical distribution of case studies, with location-based evidence concentrated in China and the USA and additional coverage across Continental Europe. Section 5.4 reviews what emissions are reported and how they are calculated; CO₂ dominates (followed by CO and NO_x), and HBEFA-based methods are most common in the corpus. Finally, Section 5.5 evaluates validation practices, noting that many studies report no validation and that those that do often rely on standard fit metrics such as GEH, MAPE, and R^2 .

5.1 Simulation tools and study focus in the reviewed studies

Figure 11 summarizes how the selected studies are linked to different simulation tools and their focus areas.

Fig. 11 Simulation tools used in the reviewed studies and their associated study focus categories

Across all studies, a variety of simulation tools are used, with VISSIM [104] and SUMO [105] being the most common. VISSIM is a commercial microscopic simulator, emissions are often obtained via add-ons or external post-processing, and it can export vehicle trajectories for post-simulation conflict analysis (e.g., using SSAM). VISSIM is the most widely used simulator and the only one that appears across every study focus, as shown in Figure 11. Among the five study focus, it is particularly prevalent in the Geometric / Physical Design Alternatives category. It is used to compare intersection layouts, median U-turn designs, and roundabout options in terms of emissions, ride comfort, and traffic conflicts [33, 35, 44]. It also supports studies on driving behaviour and route choice, for example finding cycling routes that balance safety and pollution and building combined indicators of safety, speed variability, and emissions on urban roads [34, 37]. Other work uses VISSIM to test how connected vehicles are managed at intersections, and to assess measures such as soft urban traffic management, operation of on-street parking, and dynamic speed limits on motorways, with both emissions and safety reported for each scenario [6, 50, 68, 69, 78].

SUMO is a free and open-source microscopic simulator with integrated emission module. It can also generate detailed vehicle trajectories using its own internal SSM module for post-simulation conflict analysis. Its use is most prevalent in studies on connected vehicles and their impact on traffic operations. Some studies use it to test V2V and V2I communication strategies that aim to cut both crash risk and emissions [53, 73, 88]. Others use it to study growing shares of autonomous and connected and autonomous vehicles change the performance and safety of intersections, including

comparisons between human-driven vehicles and connected and automated vehicles [5, 38, 100]. SUMO is also used for wider traffic management questions such as speed limits, signal control, and urban speed limit policies, in some cases, safety is assessed through post-run analysis of conflicts, while others embed collision-avoidance strategies directly within the simulation [60, 61, 65].

Commercial simulators such as PARAMICS [92] and AIMSUN [106] appear less often but play a similar role in linking operations, emissions, and safety. Both tools can generate detailed vehicle trajectory outputs that support post-simulation conflict analysis, while emissions are typically estimated either through integrated environmental modules (AIMSUN) or through add-ons/external post-processing (PARAMICS), depending on configuration and licensing. In these studies, PARAMICS is used to examine eco-signal strategies for connected vehicles, signal recognition, and truck operations, using measures such as hard braking, lane changes, and incident detection to reflect collision risk alongside emissions or fuel use [9, 67, 107]. AIMSUN is used to evaluate hybrid roundabouts, speed-limit policies, eco-signal strategies for connected vehicles, and a cost–benefit comparison between a Pinavia interchange and a roundabout, combining conflict analysis and dynamic speed control with emission estimates [57, 86, 91, 108].

Large-scale agent-based tools are less common but important for city-level policy analysis. MATSim [109] is a free and open-source agent-based simulator that can be integrated with an emissions module (e.g., HBEFA-based), but it does not natively produce vehicle trajectories like other microscopic transport simulators mentioned earlier, so safety and conflict outcomes are typically derived via external or custom post-processing. In these studies, MATSim is used to analyze CO₂ reduction and accident cost impacts in Hamburg and the cost–benefit of on-demand autonomous vehicles in Berlin, by simulating daily travel patterns and route choice and then deriving emissions and safety outcomes post-simulation [40, 43]. The bespoke AgentX platform is used to model ride-hailing in Chicago, showing that electrifying Uber and Lyft fleets can reduce greenhouse gas emissions while possibly increasing crash risk and congestion-related externalities [42]. ANYLOGIC appears once, in a study of safety and emissions at a school drop-off area [59].

A small set of more specialized tools appears only once in the review but still follows the same pattern of linking emissions with safety. The custom-made simulator [48], INTEGRATION [79], and CARLA [83] are used in studies that explore different levels of connected or automated vehicles and eco-driving or eco-speed strategies. ISR-TRAFSIM [49] is used in research focused on vehicle-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-infrastructure communication, while DYNEMO [36] and EstiNet [110] appear in traffic management studies related to route guidance and speed guidance, respectively. Together, these tools show how more tailored simulators are chosen for specific questions about smarter driving and traffic control, always with both emissions and safety in view.

5.2 Scale of simulated road user populations in the reviewed studies

With these tools in mind, we next examine how many agents were simulated and what this implies for the scale of the studies. The number of simulated road users in the reviewed studies varies widely, from as few as 34 agents to as many as 750,000. Out of 86 studies, 64 include enough detail to estimate the number of simulated agents, while the remaining 22 studies do not mention any simulated road users. In many of these 64 studies, the number of agents is not reported directly but estimated from reported traffic flows and the stated simulation duration, assuming a one-hour run where no duration is given. For example, if a study reports a traffic flow of 500 vehicles per hour through an intersection but does not specify the number of simulated agents, this review assumes a one-hour simulation and therefore infers that approximately 500 agents were modelled.

On this basis, the median number of simulated road users is around 3,600, while the mean is just over 34,000, the latter is strongly influenced by a small number of very large experiments. Most applications therefore operate at a relatively modest scale: all but four of the reporting studies use fewer than 100,000 agents in total, and more than four-fifths use fewer than 10,000. Figure 12 summarizes these values on a logarithmic scale, using different symbols for each simulation tool to enhance visual clarity.

Fig. 12 Number of simulated road users in the reviewed studies by simulation tool (log scale)

At the lower end of the range, many VISSIM and SUMO based studies simulate between a few hundred and a few thousand agents in order to evaluate detailed design or control questions at isolated junctions or short corridors. Examples include work on roundabout and intersection layouts, left-turn treatments, and signal control schemes, where the focus is on vehicle trajectories and conflict patterns within a constrained network rather than on network-wide travel demand [8, 35, 44, 56, 111].

In these applications, the median number of agents per experiment is on the order of 3,000–4,000 for both VISSIM and SUMO, with occasional larger corridor studies reaching tens of thousands of agents but remaining well below the 100,000 mark. Commercial tools such as AIMSUN and specialized platforms such as ISR-TRAFSIM, INTEGRATION or CARLA follow a similar pattern: they typically simulate up to a few thousand road users to examine geometric design options, eco-signal strategies or connected vehicle control in tightly defined study areas [48, 49, 57, 79, 83, 91].

Although only four case studies involve more than 100,000 simulated road users, they are particularly significant because they showcase the capabilities of large-scale agent-based models for evaluating transport policies at the city-level. As shown in Figure 12, MATSim appears as blue triangles corresponding to two studies that simulate full day travel for large urban populations in Germany: one investigates the cost–benefit of on-demand AVs in Berlin [40], and the other evaluates CO2 reduction and accident cost impacts of transport scenarios in Hamburg [43].

Both studies apply emissions and crash cost factors to translate simulation outputs into joint environmental and safety cost estimates. A third city-wide study uses the AgentX platform, shown as a red pentagon, to model ride-hailing trips across Chicago [42]. This study combines life-cycle emissions with crash risk and congestion externalities, using cost factors to compare operational and electrification scenarios.

The fourth study, using AnyLogic (black square in Figure 12), differs in scope. Rather than simulating city-wide travel, it models a single school junction with different drop-off/pick-up configurations [59]. Although the cumulative number of simulated road users reaches 750,000, this reflects repeated runs over a school year (500 hours) rather than a large demand base. The study applies a MCDM approach to compare annual emissions and safety performance across five design alternatives. Together, these cases highlight how both city-wide and localized models can handle large populations, either through spatial coverage or extended simulation time, while also offering integrated assessments of emissions and safety.

5.3 Geographical distribution of the reviewed case studies

To contextualize the breadth of the literature, we map where these case studies have been conducted, which may not always align with the institutional locations of the author. Figure 13 maps the geographical distribution of the 86 studies reviewed. Just over one fifth of the papers (18 studies) are conducted entirely in

simulated environments, without being tied to a specific real world network or city [48, 50, 72, 84, 98, 100, 102, 112]. This is likely because many of these studies focus on new strategies involving connected and automated vehicles and next-generation traffic control (such as eco-driving and eco-speed control, signal-free intersections, and cooperative lane changing) that are not yet implemented widely in real cities. In this context, simulation provides the control, repeatability, and detailed behavioural data needed to evaluate these mechanisms systematically.

Fig. 13 Geographical distribution of the reviewed case studies

The remaining case studies (highlighted in yellow) are linked to specific locations, but they are unevenly distributed. Almost three-quarters of those are concentrated in five countries: China, USA, Germany, Portugal, and Turkey. China hosts the largest group of case studies (15 studies across 11 assessed themes), combining geometric design, traffic control, and connected-vehicle strategies. Examples include intersection design comparisons, such as alternative designs for a two-legged continuous flow intersection or left-turn waiting-area configurations [41, 113]. Further examples include intersection control comparisons, including tests of various control strategies and optimization-based control schemes [65, 114]. Additional examples include driving behaviour studies, such as guided versus unguided strategies or RL-based approaches for learning driving behaviours in autonomous driving [75, 110].

The United States forms the second largest cluster (12 studies across 7 themes), emphasizing corridor and network traffic management alongside intersection-focused work. Examples include intersection control under different traffic conditions (e.g., light and heavy traffic) and different vehicle technologies (e.g., autonomous versus human-driven vehicles) [79, 103, 107]. They also evaluate intersection designs, including comparisons between two-way stop control and other alternatives [95, 96]. Germany remains prominent (10 studies across 9 themes), particularly in connected

and automated vehicle applications, with examples including intersection control comparisons across multiple Multi-agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) strategies [65]. It also includes driving behaviour comparisons such as eco-driving in autonomous versus human-driven vehicles [76].

Portugal accounts for 8 studies across 6 themes, most frequently focusing on crosswalk placement and driving behaviour. The crosswalk studies test crosswalk relocation, shifting crosswalk locations in five-metre increments [10, 90]. Meanwhile, the driving-behaviour studies evaluate outcomes across three demand periods (morning peak, off-peak, and afternoon peak) and under increasing shares of automated vehicles [37, 85]. Turkey (6 studies across 3 themes) focuses on geometric design evaluation, comparing three intersection alternatives (signalized, roundabout, and grade-separated) [47]. Turkey-based studies also include corridor and junction layout comparisons [44, 45, 57, 115].

Beyond these clusters, the map reveals a wide but thin spread of case studies across Europe, Asia, North America, and the Global South, including work in South Korea, Jordan, India, Greece, the UAE, Cameroon, and others, as well as a small number of multi-country applications such as crosswalk design and traffic signal control schemes that span several national contexts [65, 90]. Overall, the geographical distribution shows that evidence on the emissions–safety trade-off is concentrated in a limited set of countries with strong modelling traditions. Surprisingly, the United Kingdom is absent from the reviewed case studies, despite its prominent role in transport research and policy. Many other regions, particularly in Africa, South Asia, and Latin America, remain under represented in the reviewed literature.

5.4 Reported emission types and modelling approaches in the reviewed studies

Since emissions represent the primary environmental outcome of interest, this section reviews the pollutants and modelling approaches used across studies. In the selected corpus, studies typically target pollutants that are either major GHG that trap heat by absorbing infrared radiation (e.g., CO₂, CH₄, N₂O) or harmful air pollutants, which are primarily regulated for air-quality reasons but can still influence climate indirectly (e.g., CO, NO_x, VOC/HC) or through radiative forcing as aerosols (e.g., PM, especially black carbon). The radial bar chart in Figure 14 shows the spread of emission types reported across the papers in this review.

Fig. 14 Reported emission types in the reviewed studies

The figure shows that CO₂ is by far the most frequently reported pollutant (54 times), reflecting its central role in climate policy and in the design of eco-traffic strategies. CO and NO_x follow closely, usually alongside CO₂ when studies seek to capture both greenhouse gas and local air-quality impacts [8, 78, 90]. While CO is not typically classified as a direct GHG, it is widely recognized as an indirect climate forcer because it alters atmospheric chemistry in ways that can increase methane lifetime and influence ozone formation, similarly, NO_x is not a direct GHG but contributes indirectly via its role in tropospheric ozone production.

HC and VOC appear less often and are primarily treated as air pollutants. However, they can also contribute indirectly to warming through ozone formation, meaning they are sometimes included when studies aim to reflect both air-quality and broader climate-relevant mechanisms. PM also appears less frequently, but when included it is typically motivated by sustainability or ecological objectives [80, 100, 101]. PM is not a gas and therefore not a GHG, yet it can strongly affect radiative forcing depending on its composition (e.g., black carbon warming versus reflective aerosols cooling). Other gases such as CH₄ and SO₂, as well as aggregated greenhouse-gas emissions, appears once in the corpus [42, 78].

Turning to how emissions are quantified, Figure 15 summarizes the emission modelling and calculation approaches used across the corpus. In 21 studies (24.4%), the emission method is not specified explicitly, in 9 (10.5%) of these, the description

of the simulation set-up indicates reliance on the SUMO internal emission module, which is based on HBEFA, (highlighted in orange). Among papers that do state their methodology, HBEFA is the most frequently cited source, particularly in European studies and in some Asian cases. HBEFA is used either as a curated database of emission factors differentiated by vehicle class/technology and driving conditions (e.g., average speed bands or traffic states), or via instantaneous formulations embedded within microscopic simulators to translate simulated trajectories into emission estimates [5, 72, 73, 88].

Fig. 15 Emission modelling and calculation approaches used in the reviewed studies

A further group of microscopic studies employ VT-Micro. It estimates emissions using microscopic regression functions driven by instantaneous speed and acceleration, summed across full vehicle trajectories. This makes it more sensitive to stop-go dynamics than link-based factor approaches. It is most commonly used in studies that assess intersection control for connected vehicles [51, 79]. Similarly, MOVES is used assessing intersection control and post-incident rerouting for connected vehicles [52, 101, 107]. MOVES estimates emissions by mapping vehicle activity into operating conditions (often combining speed with load/power proxies) and applying corresponding emission rates before aggregating across vehicles and time.

VSP is frequently adopted in Portuguese studies, especially those focusing on alternative geometric designs and route choice impacts [10, 34, 48]. VSP is not an emissions model like the others; it is a power-demand metric computed from second-by-second speed and acceleration (and sometimes grade). The resulting VSP values are grouped into ranges, and each range is matched to an emission rate (e.g., g/s), which is then summed over time to estimate total emissions. This makes it well suited to capturing how design and behaviour driven changes in operating conditions influence emissions. More specialized or region-specific approaches include tools such as SimaPro, EnViVer, Comprehensive Modal Emission Model (CMEM) for diesel trucks, Chinese pollution-factor models, and physics-based instantaneous power formulations tailored to particular fleets or contexts [9, 41, 55, 93, 97].

Finally, several studies adopt a monetized emission approach, where unit cost factors (sourced from national or European factor sets) are multiplied directly to simulated vehicle kilometres travelled to estimate total emission costs [40, 42, 43]. By expressing emissions and safety impacts in monetary terms, these studies translate them into a common economic metric, enabling all evaluation criteria to be compared within a single cost-based framework and communicated more clearly to stakeholders. This conversion also allows the impacts to be integrated within a broader life-cycle cost framework, where monetized operational, environmental, and safety outcomes are aggregated over the service life of the project to assess long-term net benefits and support economically grounded decision-making [95, 96].

5.5 Validation approaches used in the reviewed studies

Since the reliability of simulation results depends on how well they mirror real-world conditions, we now review the validation practices used across studies. The validation assessment examines the extent to which traffic flows, speeds, travel behaviour, emissions, and safety indicators produced by simulation models were systematically checked against external data or theoretical benchmarks. Figure 16 summarizes the validation approaches reported in the 86 studies. Out of 86, 46 report no validation at all, representing the largest single group in the corpus. This means that over half of the corpus provides no statistical fitness check on simulated and real-world traffic conditions.

Among the remaining 40 validated studies, 30 (75%) rely on a single validation metric, while 10 (25%) apply two or more complementary metrics to check different features of model performance. The majority of validated applications therefore adopt relatively light statistical fitness checks, and only a small subset uses multiple quantitative benchmarks.

Fig. 16 Validation approaches in the reviewed studies

The most commonly applied formal metric is the GEH statistic, used in 16.2% of the total validation choices. GEH is a standardized fitness indicator for comparing observed and simulated traffic flow on the road network or its components (road sections and intersections). A threshold of $GEH < 5$ is considered good fit in traffic modelling [97]. Within the corpus, the GEH statistic is primarily used to validate link-level traffic flows at intersections and along short corridors. It is applied in both infrastructure design studies, such as those evaluating crosswalk geometry, hybrid roundabouts, traffic signal control, and in behavioural studies, including route choice analysis and car-following model comparisons, among others [10, 34, 37, 44, 47, 57, 97].

The second most frequent metric is MAPE, used in 10.5% of validation choices. MAPE is commonly used as an evaluation indicator to quantify the error between the simulation and reality. Well-calibrated models in traffic studies often report MAPE within a narrow tolerance band, in this corpus, $MAPE < 5\%$ is treated as evidence of good agreement [78]. MAPE is applied to validate intersection throughput, corridor flows, left-turn treatments, on-ramp merges, and crosswalk performance, particularly in studies comparing alternative geometric layouts or eco-approach control strategies, as well as in several other design and control contexts [41, 58, 94, 113].

The third most frequent metric is R^2 used in 7.6% of all validation choices. R^2 (coefficient of determination) measures the proportion of variance in the observed traffic volumes that is explained by the simulated volumes. In most transportation simulation contexts, R^2 values ≥ 0.80 are indicative of a good model fit [37]. Many applications report GEH and/or MAPE alongside R^2 to establish baseline traffic realism. Beyond the design comparison studies noted above, R^2 is also used to validate automated-vehicle penetration effects on traffic and network wide cooperative control, and it appears in several other modelling contexts [35, 73, 85, 90].

A smaller proportion of studies (4.8%) validate using RMSE and normalized variants

(e.g., NRMSE or RMSN). In all cases, they are used to quantify the magnitude of error (i.e., the discrepancy) between the observed and simulated data, values closer to zero indicate better agreement [10, 33, 61, 82]. Another error-based metric is RE, which is reported in three studies (2.9%) [46, 87, 115].

Travel time validation using floating car data (4.8%) is another approach used to assess how closely simulated point-to-point travel times match those observed in the field. Here, observed travel times come from repeated test-vehicle runs, whereas simulated travel times are obtained from the vehicle trajectory output of the simulator, and validation is performed by comparing the mean travel times. In the corpus, this method appears alongside other validation approaches mentioned earlier [8, 10, 85].

Beyond the standard metrics above, the corpus includes several alternative validation approaches (5.7%). These include animation-based validation, comparisons of simulation outputs with loop-detector volumes, U-value criteria, and the Van Aerde model, among others [59, 62, 89, 101]. Additionally, 3.8% of the studies use heuristic calibration, reporting no formal statistical thresholds, but manually adjusting parameters until flows or conflicts appear plausible [36, 55, 68].

Two notable large-scale city models adopt iterative or behavioural validation rather than simple link flow checks. A MATSim Berlin case study performs iterative calibration by using CaDyTS to adjust agent’s plan choice probabilities, which influence departure time and route choice within the simulation. The calibration process continues until simulated traffic flows patterns became consistent with the actual traffic patterns observed at counting stations in Berlin [40]. A separate MATSim Hamburg study validates by comparing observed and simulated modal split, and modal distance distributions against mobility in Germany [43]. Here, consistency in mode shares acts as the realism benchmark before CO2 reduction and accident cost scenarios are jointly assessed.

Overall, these findings point to a “fit-for-purpose” validation strategy. Use GEH when reproducing link or turning-movement flows, as it is the most established count-based metric. Use MAPE (and RMSE-type measures) when the aim is to quantify average error magnitudes for throughput, corridor performance, or design alternatives. Use R^2 to show that the model captures the overall variance in observed volumes, ideally alongside GEH or MAPE. For studies concerned with network performance and realistic travel times, use travel time validation. Finally, in large-scale, policy-focused or scenario-driven city models, iterative calibration, such as CaDyTS-based plan adjustment, and behavioural validation, including modal split and trip-distance distributions, are more appropriate for capturing system-level realism than relying solely on local link flow thresholds.

6 Conclusion and Future work

This SLR provides the first structured synthesis of transport studies that examines emissions and road safety together, an important but under-studied intersection in the transport modelling literature. Using a PRISMA framework to identify relevant works and a concept-driven taxonomy developed following Nickerson et al.’s iterative method, we reviewed 86 transport studies. We categorized these across eight key methodological dimensions and synthesized the evidence through two organizing lenses (study focus and road safety assessment approach), to support comparison across diverse modelling setups.

A central aim of this review was to examine a widely held policy assumption: that strategies designed to reduce emissions also tend to improve safety. The evidence reviewed here suggests that this relationship is common, but not universal, and depends on the type of intervention.

On the encouraging side, the corpus shows a strong concentration of results in the joint-improvement region when both outcomes are measured in comparable terms. In the subset of studies reporting both conflict change and emission change, Win–Win outcomes dominate (47 cases), and “Lose–Lose” outcomes are absent. This supports a practical heuristic: interventions that improve operational efficiency and reshape interaction patterns through measures such as better control, speed management, and safer network design often deliver lower emissions and fewer conflicts.

However, this heuristic is not a guarantee. A minority of studies reports trade-offs where emission reductions coincide with increased conflicts (and vice versa). Conflicts may rise with higher cycling volumes at roundabouts when the specialized infrastructure is not adapted [8]. Truck lane restrictions can slightly cut emissions but raise safety risk on motorways [9]. Crosswalk placement near roundabout exits improves safety at the cost of higher emissions and delay compared with midblock locations [10]. Overall, whether “green” is also “safe” depends on exposure, interaction density, and behavioural adaptation.

The review also highlights several limitations: only a small number of studies use large-scale agent-based simulation to test mode shift policies (e.g., cycling uptake or public transport promotion) to assess potential safety–emissions trade-offs. Moreover, although some policy effect studies apply cost-based (monetized) frameworks to express emissions and safety impacts on a common monetary scale, external costs are usually treated as static and calculated post-simulation, so they do not influence agent decision-making within the model.

Even where a financial incentive is introduced (e.g., in one Hamburg-based scenario), the limited change in modal share suggests that the incentive is implemented as part of the scenario design rather than as an endogenous behavioural mechanism, and therefore has only a marginal effect on reducing emissions and accident costs [43]. Moreover, the crash-cost calculation adopted across these studies is highly simplified,

and is commonly estimated by multiplying vehicle kilometres travelled by national fatality rates, or crash-cost factors from the literature, or values taken from national transport appraisal handbooks [40, 42, 43]. While this exposure-based method provides a straightforward distance-based proxy for risk, it cannot capture several critical contextual dimensions, including accident severity, the time and location of occurrence, and the types of road users involved (e.g., pedestrians and cyclists).

These findings point to three clear directions for future work:

- More large-scale, behaviourally validated models that integrate emissions and safety as joint decision criteria, embedded within city-scale digital twins rather than isolated junction or corridor studies.
- Expanded use of cost-based frameworks that monetize environmental and safety outcomes, enabling systematic comparison of alternatives and explicit valuation of trade-offs, including those arising from mode-shift and incentive-based strategies.
- Improved mode-specific safety representation in joint emissions–safety evaluations, moving beyond exposure-based crash costing toward risk and severity estimates that reflect where and to whom harm occurs, particularly for vulnerable road users.

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Appendix A

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
CADYTS	Calibration of Dynamic Traffic Simulations
GEH	Geoffrey E. Havers Statistic
HBEFA	Handbook Emission Factors for Road Transport
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
MCDM	Multi-criteria Decision Making
MOVES	Motor Vehicle Emission Simulator
MSC	Monetized Safety Cost
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RE	Relative Error
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SSM	Surrogate Safety Measures
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
VSP	Vehicle Specific Power
VT-Micro	Virginia Tech Microscopic Energy and Emission Model

References

- [1] IPCC: Sixth assessment report. Report (2022). <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg3/chapter/chapter-10/>
- [2] Sfyridis, A.: Road transport and emissions modelling in england and wales: A machine learning modelling approach using spatial data. Thesis, UCL (University College London) (2022)
- [3] ERSO: Road safety: 20,640 people died in a road crash last year – progress remains too slow. European Road Safety Observatory (2023). https://transport.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/road-safety-20640-people-died-road-crash-last-year-progress-remains-too-slow-2023-10-19_en
- [4] DoT: Reported road casualties in Great Britain, provisional estimates: year ending June 2023. Department of Transport (2023). <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/reported-road-casualties-in-great-britain-provisional-estimates-year-ending-june-2023>
- [5] Guo, J., Cheng, L., Wang, S.: Cotv: Cooperative control for traffic light signals and connected autonomous vehicles using deep reinforcement learning. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **24**(10), 10501–10512 (2023)
- [6] Zhang, Z.H., Sun, D.Z., Lv, J.P., Sai, J., Faruqi, M.: An optimization model for dynamic speed control in urban freeway networks. In: *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, vol. 668-669, pp. 1458–1461. Trans Tech Publications Ltd
- [7] He, Q., Meng, Y., Tan, W., Tian, X., Liu, S., Yang, H., Shao, Y., Pan, B.: Analyzing the relationship between the efficiency and safety of a turbo roundabout by the factor analysis method. *Heliyon* **10**(4) (2024)
- [8] Bahmankhah, B., Fernandes, P., Coelho, M.C.: Cycling at intersections: A multi-objective assessment for traffic, emissions and safety. *Transport* **34**(2), 225–236 (2019)
- [9] Yang, C.H., Regan, A.C.: A multi-criteria decision support methodology for implementing truck operation strategies. *Transportation* **40**(3), 713–728 (2013)
- [10] Fernandes, P., Fontes, T., Pereira, S.R., Roupail, N.M., Coelho, M.C.: Multicriteria assessment of crosswalk location in urban roundabout corridors. *Transportation Research Record* **2517**, 37–47 (2015)
- [11] Ahmed, H.U., Huang, Y., Lu, P., Bridgelall, R.: Technology developments and impacts of connected and autonomous vehicles: An overview. *Smart Cities* **5**(1), 382–404 (2022)
- [12] Alghamdi, T., Mostafi, S., Abdelkader, G., Elgazzar, K.: A comparative study on traffic modeling techniques for predicting and simulating traffic behavior.

Future Internet **14**(10) (2022)

- [13] Alshayeb, S., Stevanovic, A., Mitrovic, N., Espino, E.: Traffic signal optimization to improve sustainability: A literature review. *Energies* **15**(22) (2022)
- [14] Ansarinejad, M., Ansarinejad, K., Lu, P., Huang, Y., Tolliver, D.: Autonomous vehicles in rural areas: A review of challenges, opportunities, and solutions. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)* **15**(8) (2025)
- [15] Bastarianto, F.F., Hancock, T.O., Choudhury, C.F., Manley, E.: Agent-based models in urban transportation: review, challenges, and opportunities. *European Transport Research Review* **15**(1) (2023)
- [16] Calderón, F., Miller, E.J.: A literature review of mobility services: definitions, modelling state-of-the-art, and key considerations for a conceptual modelling framework. *Transport Reviews* **40**(3), 312–332 (2020)
- [17] Campi, E., Mastinu, G., Previati, G., Studer, L., Uccello, L.: Roundabouts: Traffic simulations of connected and automated vehicles - a state of the art. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **25**(5), 3305–3325 (2024)
- [18] Divasson-J, A., Macarulla, A.M., Garcia, J.I., Borges, C.E.: Agent-based modeling in urban human mobility: A systematic review. *Cities* **158** (2025)
- [19] Haghighi, M., Miller, E.J.: Week-long activity-based modelling: a review of the existing models and datasets and a comprehensive conceptual framework. *Transport Reviews* **45**(1), 119–148 (2025)
- [20] Jang, S., Park, J., Yu, G., Hwang, J.: Tools for estimating traffic emissions considering spatial scales and mitigation strategies: A systematic review. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation* **19**(5), 431–445 (2025)
- [21] Jing, P., Hu, H., Zhan, F., Chen, Y., Shi, Y.: Agent-based simulation of autonomous vehicles: A systematic literature review. *IEEE Access* **8**, 79089–79103 (2020)
- [22] Li, J., Rombaut, E., Vanhaverbeke, L.: A systematic review of agent-based models for autonomous vehicles in urban mobility and logistics: Possibilities for integrated simulation models. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* **89** (2021)
- [23] Madziel, M.: Vehicle emission models and traffic simulators: A review. *Energies* **16**(9) (2023)
- [24] Manglano-Redondo, P., Paricio-Garcia, A., Lopez-Carmona, M.A.: Dynamic low-emission zones for urban mobility: A systematic review. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)* **15**(6) (2025)

- [25] Marwal, A., Silva, E.: Literature review of accessibility measures and models used in land use and transportation planning in last 5 years. *Journal of Geographical Sciences* **32**(3), 560–584 (2022)
- [26] Nguyen, N.A., Schweizer, J., Rupi, F.: Large-scale activity-based demand generation modeling: A literature review and exploration of potential approaches. *Transportation Engineering* **20** (2025)
- [27] Noaen, M., Naik, A., Goodman, L., Crebo, J., Abrar, T., Abad, Z.S.H., Bazzan, A.L.C., Far, B.: Reinforcement learning in urban network traffic signal control: A systematic literature review. *Expert Systems with Applications* **199** (2022)
- [28] Ren, R., Li, H., Han, T., Tian, C., Zhang, C., Zhang, J., Proctor, R.W., Chen, Y., Feng, Y.: Vehicle crash simulations for safety: Introduction of connected and automated vehicles on the roadways. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* **186** (2023)
- [29] Serena, L., Marzolla, M., D’Angelo, G., Ferretti, S.: A review of multilevel modeling and simulation for human mobility and behavior. *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory* **127** (2023)
- [30] Singh, M.K., Rao, K.R.: Cellular automata models for signalised and unsignalised intersections with special attention to mixed traffic flow: A review. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems* **14**(12), 1507–1516 (2020)
- [31] Stankov, I., Garcia, L.M.T., Masculli, M.A., Montes, F., Meisel, J.D., Gouveia, N., Sarmiento, O.L., Rodriguez, D.A., Hammond, R.A., Caiaffa, W.T., Diez Roux, A.V.: A systematic review of empirical and simulation studies evaluating the health impact of transportation interventions. *Environmental Research* **186** (2020)
- [32] Nickerson, R.C., Varshney, U., Muntermann, J.: A method for taxonomy development and its application in information systems. *European journal of information systems* **22**(3), 336–359 (2013)
- [33] Alhadidi, T.I., Matarneh, S.T., Tahoona, A.A.: The feasibility and operational performance of implementation median u-turn intersections: A critic method. *Periodica Polytechnica Transportation Engineering* **52**(3), 257–269 (2024)
- [34] Bahmankhah, B., Coelho, M.C.: Multi-objective optimization for short distance trips in an urban area: Choosing between motor vehicle or cycling mobility for a safe, smooth and less polluted route **27**, 428–435 (2017)
- [35] Bahmankhah, B., Macedo, E., Fernandes, P., Coelho, M.C.: Micro driving behaviour in different roundabout layouts: Pollutant emissions, vehicular jerk, and traffic conflicts analysis. In: *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 62, pp. 501–508. Elsevier B.V.

- [36] Chen, Q., Stauss, H.J.: Evaluating traffic effects of a route guidance system by dynamic simulation. *Simulation Practice and Theory* **5**(7-8), 793–804 (1997)
- [37] Ferreira, E., Fernandes, P., Macedo, E., Coelho, M.C.: Driving safety-volatility-emissions integrated indicator-application to urban road environment. In: *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 86, pp. 572–579. Elsevier B.V.
- [38] Li, H., Dong, W., Lu, L., Wang, Y., Wang, X.: Distributed cooperative driving strategy for connected automated vehicles at unsignalized intersections based on monte carlo method. *Journal of Advanced Transportation* **2024** (2024)
- [39] Park, H., Bhamidipati, C.S., Smith, B.L.: Development and evaluation of enhanced intellidrive-enabled lane changing advisory algorithm to address freeway merge conflict. *Transportation Research Record* (2243), 146–157 (2011)
- [40] Carreyre, F., Chouaki, T., Coulombel, N., Berrada, J., Bouillaut, L., Hörl, S.: On-demand autonomous vehicles in berlin: A cost-benefit analysis. *Transportation Research Record* **2678**(5), 13–30 (2024)
- [41] Dong, S., Yang, Z., Xu, C., Tian, Z.Z., Liu, P.: Multiobjective evaluation of left-turn waiting areas at signalized intersections in china. *Transportation Research Record* **2553**(1), 138–149 (2016)
- [42] Mohan, A., Bruchon, M., Michalek, J., Vaishnav, P.: Life cycle air pollution, greenhouse gas, and traffic externality benefits and costs of electrifying uber and lyft. *Environmental Science and Technology* **57**(23), 8524–8535 (2023)
- [43] Schlenther, T., Wagner, P., Rybczak, G., Nagel, K., Bieker-Walz, L., Ortgiese, M.: Simulation-based investigation of transport scenarios for hamburg. In: *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 201, pp. 587–593. Elsevier B.V.
- [44] Alemdar, K.D., Tortum, A., Kaya, O., Atalay, A.: Interdisciplinary evaluation of intersection performances—a microsimulation-based MCDA. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* **13**(4), 1–17 (2021)
- [45] Bayata, H.F., Bas, F.I., Mengi, G.S.: Traffic impact analysis of a regional shopping center using microsimulation with the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) approach. *Iranian Journal of Science and Technology - Transactions of Civil Engineering* **49**(1), 975–983 (2025)
- [46] Bayrak, O.U., Abret, N.E.: A multi-criteria decision for determining the appropriate junction design type: AHP approach with microsimulation. *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin* **28**(10), 7183–7195 (2019)
- [47] Bayrak, O.U., Bayata, H.F.: Multi-criteria decision-based safety evaluation using microsimulation. *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers: Transport* **173**(5), 345–357 (2020)

- [48] Bakibillah, A.S.M., Kamal, M.A.S., Tan, C.P., Hayakawa, T., Imura, J.I.: Optimal eco-driving scheme for reducing energy consumption and carbon emissions on curved roads. *Heliyon* **10**(1) (2024)
- [49] Bento, L.C., Parafita, R., Rakha, H.A., Nunes, U.J.: A study of the environmental impacts of intelligent automated vehicle control at intersections via V2V and V2I communications. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems: Technology, Planning, and Operations* **23**(1), 41–59 (2019)
- [50] Chen, Z., Lin, P., He, H., Zhuo, F.: Intersection coordination control strategy for intelligent connected vehicle. In: *SAE Technical Papers*. SAE International
- [51] Ding, J., Xu, H., Hu, J., Zhang, Y.: The impact of centralized cooperative intersection control on traffic flow characteristics. In: *2017 4th International Conference on Transportation Information and Safety, ICTIS 2017 - Proceedings*, pp. 858–864. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc.
- [52] Jeong, E., Oh, C., Lee, G.: Emission evaluation of inter-vehicle safety warning information systems. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* **41**, 106–117 (2015)
- [53] Gunathilake, O., De Silva, S., Nimhara Kumari, S., Nikeshala, H., Karunanayake, P.: Implementing a vehicular communication network to minimize accident-related traffic congestion in the southern expressway of sri lanka. In: *2023 IEEE World AI IoT Congress, AIIoT 2023*, pp. 177–183. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc.
- [54] Campisi, T., Canale, A., Tesoriere, G., Renčelj, M.: The newest public transport system applied to turbo roundabouts. *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers: Engineering Sustainability* **173**(6), 315–322 (2020)
- [55] Cantisani, G., Panesso, J.D.C., Del Serrone, G., Di Mascio, P., Gentile, G., Loprencipe, G., Moretti, L.: Re-design of a road node with 7d bim: Geometrical, environmental and microsimulation approaches to implement a benefit-cost analysis between alternatives. *Automation in Construction* **135** (2022)
- [56] Hong, S., Jung, S., Oh, C., Park, S.: A novel method to integrate speed and emissions characteristics in pavement marking design. *KSCE Journal of Civil Engineering* **22**(12), 5178–5186 (2018)
- [57] User, Y., Ilyas, S., Tinaztepe, G.: Performance evaluation of a hybrid roundabout using a microscopic simulation. *Baltic Journal of Road and Bridge Engineering* **16**(3), 47–81 (2021)
- [58] Liu, Y., Pan, B., Song, R., Zong, L.: Evaluation of sustainable design method for three-lane entrance ramps on expressways in urban areas: A case study of Xi'an, China. *IEEE Access* **11**, 117714–117728 (2023)

- [59] Magableh, G.M., Mumani, A.A.: Simulation based-MCDM approach for evaluating traffic solutions. *Promet - Traffic and Transportation* **34**(1), 117–133 (2022)
- [60] Du, S., Razavi, S., Absulsattar, H.: Variable speed limits control for smart work zone with connected vehicles. In: *Proceedings of the International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction*, pp. 1120–1127. International Association for Automation and Robotics in Construction (IAARC)
- [61] Lu, Q.L., Qurashi, M., Antoniou, C.: Simulation-based policy analysis: The case of urban speed limits. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice* **175** (2023)
- [62] Yang, J., Wang, P.: Multi-segment variable speed predictive control strategy for eliminating traffic bottlenecks in emergency cases on super-long-span bridges. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)* **14**(24) (2024)
- [63] Hu, L., Tang, J., Zou, G., Li, Z., Zeng, J., Li, M.: Simulation optimization of highway hard shoulder running based on multi-agent deep deterministic policy gradient algorithm. *Alexandria Engineering Journal* **117**, 99–115 (2025)
- [64] Lipeng, H., Jinjun, T., Wang, Z., Li, Z., Li, M., Jie, Z.: Optimization of hard shoulder running on highways using multi-agent reinforcement learning considering emergency vehicles. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 1–22 (2025)
- [65] Nie, L., Qi, D., Liu, B., Li, P., Bao, H., He, H.: Cmrn: Collaborative multi-agent reinforcement learning for multi-objective traffic signal control. *IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics* (2025)
- [66] Tran, Q.H., Do, V.M., Dinh, T.H.: Traffic signal timing optimization for isolated urban intersections considering environmental problems and non-motorized vehicles by using constrained optimization solutions. *Innovative Infrastructure Solutions* **7**(5) (2022)
- [67] Nakazawa, M., Fukuda, A., Okamura, M., Suzuki, H.: Impact of introducing signal recognition enhancement system on traffic flow at signalized intersection. In: *IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems, Proceedings, ITSC*, pp. 1306–1309
- [68] Karatsoli, M., Karakikes, I., Nathanail, E.: Urban traffic management utilizing soft measures: A case study of volos city. In: *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 879, pp. 655–662. Springer
- [69] Salah Jasim, N., Abdul Ameer Alwash, A.: Sustainable operation of on-street parking within hilla city by simulation model (VISSIM) with surrogate safety assessment model (SSAM). In: *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental*

- [70] Dong, C., Wang, H., Chen, Q., Ni, D., Li, Y.: Simulation-based assessment of multilane separate freeways at toll station area: A case study from huludao toll station on shenshan freeway. *Sustainability* **11**(11), 3057 (2019)
- [71] Mirbakhsh, A., Lee, J., Besenski, D.: Development of a signal-free intersection control system for CAVs and corridor level impact assessment. *Future Transportation* **3**(2), 552–567 (2023)
- [72] Tettamanti, T., Mohammadi, A., Asadi, H., Varga, I.: A two-level urban traffic control for autonomous vehicles to improve network-wide performance. In: *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 27, pp. 913–920. Elsevier B.V.
- [73] Walch, M., Neubauer, M.: Integrated evaluation of C-ITS services: Synergistic effects of GLOSA and CACC on traffic efficiency and sustainability. *Sustainability* **17**(19), 8855 (2025)
- [74] Khosravinia, K., Wang, S., Lin, X.: Eco-driving control of connected and automated hybrid electric vehicles on multi-lane roads using model predictive control. In: *SAE Technical Papers*. SAE International
- [75] Hu, W., Hu, J., Liu, Y., Zhou, J., Su, M.: Integrated decision-making methodology based on reinforcement learning and imitation learning for automated commercial vehicles in the urban traffic environment. *International Journal of Vehicle Systems Modelling and Testing* **18**(3), 245–266 (2024)
- [76] Wang, S., Lin, X.: Eco-driving control of connected and automated hybrid vehicles in mixed driving scenarios. *Applied Energy* **271** (2020)
- [77] Halbach, M., Markowski, R., Junghans, M.: Multi-criteria traffic control with scalable optimisation goals involving cyclists a SUMO study. In: *2024 Smart Cities Symposium Prague, SCSP 2024 - Proceedings*. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc.
- [78] Elawady, A., Abuzwidah, M., Zeiada, W.: The benefits of using connected vehicles system on traffic delay and safety at urban signalized intersections. In: *2022 Advances in Science and Engineering Technology International Conferences, ASET 2022*. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc.
- [79] Kamalanathsharma, R.K., Rakha, H.A., Yang, H.: Networkwide impacts of vehicle ecospeed control in the vicinity of traffic signalized intersection. *Transportation Research Record* **2503**(1), 91–99 (2015)
- [80] Li, Z., Chitturi, M.V., Yu, L., Bill, A.R., Noyce, D.A.: Sustainability effects of next-generation intersection control for autonomous vehicles. *Transport* **30**(3), 342–352 (2015)

- [81] Lin, P., Chen, C., Huang, X., Ran, B.: Cooperative lane-change on the main-line of highway in a connected vehicle environment. In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1910. IOP Publishing Ltd
- [82] Wu, S., Zou, Y., Liu, D., Chen, X., Wang, Y., Moeinaddini, A.: Investigating traffic characteristics at freeway merging areas in heterogeneous mixed-flow environments. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* **17**(5) (2025)
- [83] Xiong, Z., Hu, P., Li, N., Chen, X., Chen, W., Wang, H., Xie, N., Li, Y., Dong, C.: Modelling and simulation of mixed traffic flow with dedicated lanes for connected automated vehicles. *Expert Systems with Applications* **274** (2025)
- [84] Yavuz, M.N., Özen, H.: Investigating the impact of connected and autonomous vehicles on a grid urban network considering different driving behaviors. *Advances in Transportation Studies* **63**, 191–206 (2024)
- [85] Marques, D., Bandeira, J., Coelho, M.C.: Traffic, emissions and safety impacts of automated vehicles connecting a university and a science park, 1–6 (2021)
- [86] Rahimov, K., Motamadnia, A., Samadi, S.: Technical and economic evaluation of pinavia interchange in comparison with roundabout intersection by AIMSUN. *Civil engineering journal* **2**(3), 102–112 (2016)
- [87] Du, S., Razavi, S.: Variable speed limit for freeway work zone with capacity drop using discrete-time sliding mode control. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering* **33**(2), 04019001 (2019)
- [88] Outay, F., Kamoun, F., Kaisser, F., Alterri, D., Yasar, A.: V2V and V2I communications for traffic safety and CO2 emission reduction: A performance evaluation. In: *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 151, pp. 353–360. Elsevier B.V.
- [89] Tawfeek, M.H., El-Basyouny, K.: Network-level comparison of various forward collision warning algorithms. *Simulation* **95**(4), 313–325 (2019)
- [90] Fernandes, P., Salamati, K., Roupail, N.M., Coelho, M.C.: The effect of a roundabout corridor’s design on selecting the optimal crosswalk location: A multi-objective impact analysis. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation* **11**(3), 206–220 (2017)
- [91] Chaves, C., Vasconcelos, A.L., Bastos Silva, A., Almeida, R.: Microsimulation-based evaluation of a 30 km/h zone. *Road and Rail Infrastructure*, V.; Lakusic, S., Ed, 1341–1347 (2018)
- [92] Paramics, Q.: PARAMICS (2010). <http://www.paramics-online.com/index.php>
- [93] Ganguly, S., Dutta, M., Ghosh, T., Ahmed, M.A., Maitra, B.: Systemic approach

- to revamp unsignalized intersections using multi-criteria decision making: a comparison of alternative solutions. *Advances in Transportation Studies* **57**, 31–48 (2022)
- [94] Yang, Z., Liu, P., Xu, X., Xu, C.: Multiobjective evaluation of midblock crosswalks on urban streets based on topsis and entropy methods. *Transportation Research Record* **2586**, 59–71 (2016)
- [95] Yang, Z., Liu, P., Zhang, Y., Ragland, D.: Multi-objective analysis of using u-turns as alternatives to direct left turns at two-way stop-controlled intersections. *Journal of Advanced Transportation* **50**(4), 389–405 (2016)
- [96] Yang, Z., Zhang, Y., Zhu, R., Zhang, Y.: Multiobjective evaluation in countermeasure selection at two-way stop-controlled intersections considering traffic operation, safety, and environment. *Transportation Research Record* **2635**(1), 36–45 (2017)
- [97] Biszko, K., Oskarbski, J., Żarski, K.: Impact of wiedemann 74 and wiedemann 99 car-following models on estimating level of safety and emissions on signal-controlled intersections using microscopic simulations. *Archives of Transport* **72**(4), 43–73 (2024)
- [98] Lee, J., Park, B.: Development and evaluation of a cooperative vehicle intersection control algorithm under the connected vehicles environment. *IEEE transactions on intelligent transportation systems* **13**(1), 81–90 (2012)
- [99] Sharma, S., Bhojannawar, S.S.: V2I communication coverage analysis for VANET: A case study for city of Bengaluru, India, 165–173 (2025)
- [100] Reddy, R., Almeida, L., Santos, P.M., Tovar, E.: Comparing the ecological footprint of intersection management protocols for human/autonomous scenarios. In: 2020 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems, ITSC 2020. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc.
- [101] Shin, H., Ko, J., Lee, G., Oh, C.: Evaluating the environmental impact on connected vehicles during freeway accidents using vissim with probe vehicle data. *Electronic Research Archive* **32**(4), 2955–2975 (2024)
- [102] Tran, Q.D., Bae, S.H.: Comprehensive automated driving maneuvers under a non-signalized intersection adopting deep reinforcement learning. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)* **12**(19) (2022)
- [103] Wang, Z., Wu, G., Barth, M.J.: Cooperative eco-driving at signalized intersections in a partially connected and automated vehicle environment. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **21**(5), 2029–2038 (2019)
- [104] Fellendorf, M., Vortisch, P.: Microscopic traffic flow simulator VISSIM. In:

Fundamentals of Traffic Simulation, pp. 63–93. Springer. (2010)

- [105] Behrisch, M., Bieker, L., Erdmann, J., Krajzewicz, D.: Sumo—simulation of urban mobility: an overview. In: Proceedings of SIMUL 2011, The Third International Conference on Advances in System Simulation
- [106] Barceló, J., Casas, J., Ferrer, J., García, D.: Modelling advanced transport telematic applications with microscopic simulators: The case of AIMSUN2. In: Traffic and Mobility: Simulation—Economics—Environment, pp. 205–221. Springer. (1999)
- [107] Zhao, Y., Wagh, A., Hou, Y., Hulme, K., Qiao, C., Sadek, A.W.: Integrated traffic-driving-networking simulator for the design of connected vehicle applications: Eco-signal case study. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems: Technology, Planning, and Operations* **20**(1), 75–87 (2016)
- [108] Mintsis, E., Vlahogianni, E.I., Mitsakis, E., Aifadopoulou, G.: Advisory versus automated dynamic eco-driving at signalized intersections: lessons learnt from empirical evidence and simulation experiments. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems* **28**(6), 1044–1063 (2024)
- [109] Horni, A., Nagel, K., Axhausen, K.W.: Introducing MATSim. In: Multi-Agent Transport Simulation MATSim. Ubiquity Press. (2016)
- [110] Zhang, Z., Zhang, T., Wang, J., Liu, S., Wang, R.: Research on speed guidance strategy of traffic platoon based on “time block”. In: *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence and Applications*, vol. 314, pp. 287–295. IOS Press BV
- [111] Ngossaha, J.M., Pidy, L.T.P., Karunathilake, T., Förster, A., Bowong, S.: Advancing urban mobility in developing countries: A mobile rsu approach for sustainable transportation. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems* **18**(12), 2502–2519 (2024)
- [112] Shen, J., Wang, Y., Wang, H., Li, C.: Optimization of autonomous vehicle safe passage at intersections based on crossing risk degree. *Symmetry* **17**(6), 893 (2025)
- [113] Pan, B., Luo, S., Ying, J., Shao, Y., Liu, S., Li, X., Lei, J.: Evaluation and analysis of cfi schemes with different length of displaced left-turn lanes with entropy method. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* **13**(12) (2021)
- [114] Xu, Y., Zhang, Y., Wu, X.: Research and simulation implementation of self-driving vehicle trajectory optimization in networked intersection environment. SAE Technical Paper, 01–7194 (2025)
- [115] Abret, N.E., Bayrak, O.U.: The determination of convenient junction type utilizing from estimated traffic data with ahp method. *Iranian Journal of Science*

